

Workshop Proposal

Title:

Robotics for neurorehabilitation: technological advances and clinical translation

Organizers:

- Stefano Mazzoleni, Associate Professor, Department of Electrical and Information Engineering, Politecnico di Bari, Italy.
- Nevio Luigi Tagliamonte, Tenure Track Assistant Professor, Research Unit of Advanced Robotics and Human-Centered Technologies, Università Campus Bio-Medico di Roma, Italy.

Duration and format:

Two-hour workshop, with invited engineering speakers with a focus on technology design and clinical translation. 90 minutes will be dedicated to the presentation (including Q&A) from 5 invited speakers and 30 minutes will be dedicated to a round table for discussion.

Abstract:

Robotic devices are becoming increasingly relevant in neurorehabilitation to support functional assessment and therapy. The design of such systems is extremely complex and also the effectiveness is still under continuous investigation in experimental trials. Design and actual translation into clinical applications are highly interwoven and together pose several open challenges.

This workshop aims at soliciting a discussion on recent technological designs and steps towards clinical translation, i.e. at merging bioengineering, robotics and clinical perspectives on key aspects to be addressed for rehabilitation robotic technologies and their effective application in the research context of experimental trials and in the clinical daily practice.

Participants and expected attendees:

Speakers from the engineering and robotics domain, still with and a strong link with clinical applications, are invited and are all confirmed. Attendees from both the clinical and engineering domains are expected to be attracted due to the clinically oriented nature of the workshop.

List of speakers:

- Cecilia De Vicariis, Assistant Professor, University of Genova, Italy
- Tommaso Proietti, Assistant Professor, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Italy
- Alessia Nocco, Lecturer, University of Newcastle, UK
- Maria Pozzi, Assistant Professor, University of Siena, Italy
- Francesco Scotto di Luzio, Assistant Professor, Università Campus Bio-Medico di Roma, Italy

Possible impact and products:

Initiatives to improve impact:

- The intrinsic hybrid nature of the workshop, with topics from engineering domain and clinical applications, is expected to promote cross-fertilization among the two areas and also to improve the possible contact of clinical researchers and also rehabilitation professionals with the I-RIM community. A similar format was already successfully explored in the workshops arranged by the same organizers during I-RIM 2022 and 2023 conference editions.
- As a tangible product of the workshop, interested speakers will have the opportunity to prepare shareable short pitch videos (2 min), including key take-home messages from the workshop presentations, links to bibliographic items or online resources and any other relevant references to useful material.
- To maximize the impact and to improve resonance and participation, we propose to group all perspective workshops compatible with the themes in the proposed one in a *“Series of Workshops on Robotics and Intelligent Machines for Rehabilitation”* under the umbrella of the *I-RIM Working Group on Rehabilitation Robotics* (chaired by the organizers of this workshop).

Keywords:

Robotic technologies for neurorehabilitation, robots in experimental trials, robots in clinical practice.